

Supplementary Material 6: Analytic Outputs

- a. Ammunition study: rotated factor matrix
- b. Cat management study: rotated factor matrix
- c. Ammunition study: factor array
- d. Cat management study: factor array

The equivalents for the translocation study can be found in the main text (Tables 3 and 4).

S6a: Ammunition study: rotated factor matrix

The loadings indicate the extent to which each Q-sort is associated with each of the study factors following rotation. * indicates which factor each Q-sort is significantly loaded on (i.e. $\geq \pm 0.34$ at $p < 0.01$). For example, sorts 3 and 5 significantly load on to Factor 1 and contribute to the weighted average derived from the array which exemplifies Factor 1 (Table 1; Fig. S1). Q-sorts 1 and 30 are confounded, i.e. they significantly load on to both factors.

Sort number	Factor 1	Factor 2
1	0.6684	-0.4248
2	0.2244	*0.7025
3	*0.5362	0.2377
4	0.0096	*0.8426
5	*0.6077	0.1417
6	*0.4084	-0.0330
7	*0.5248	-0.0383
8	*0.4316	0.2421
9	*0.5574	0.2656
10	*0.6947	0.2477
11	-0.1989	*0.7495
12	*0.6766	-0.0755
13	0.0146	*0.6006
14	*0.6967	0.1362
15	*0.7434	0.0074
16	0.0532	*0.5185
17	0.0065	*0.6312
18	*0.3381	0.1736
19	0.2259	*0.7108
20	*0.6856	-0.0933
21	*0.3842	0.3290
22	0.2094	*0.5258
23	-0.0807	*0.7516
24	0.2837	*0.6375
25	-0.1903	*0.7204
26	*0.5973	0.0711
27	*0.6639	-0.0979
28	*0.6313	-0.2830
29	*0.5579	0.1875
30	0.4762	0.4972
% explained variance	22.7	20.2
Eigenvalue	6.8	6.1

S6b: Cat management study: rotated factor matrix. Output displaying the loadings for each participant's sort on each of the extracted factors. Significantly loading sorts that contribute to the derived factor arrays are highlighted with bold type and an *.

	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3	Factor 4	Factor 5
1	0.3316	0.1727	0.654*	0.1025	0.1052
2	0.5073*	-0.0316	0.1642	0.4556	-0.1274
3	0.5673	0.1318	-0.38	0.5532	-0.011
4	0.0491	0.3309	0.6328*	0.1113	-0.04
5	-0.0487	0.0742	0.3567	0.7063*	-0.0327
6	0.6105*	0.1968	-0.0005	-0.1708	0.4572
7	0.3335	0.5411*	0.2181	0.1102	-0.0496
8	0.0083	0.1188	0.1464	0.5004*	0.2228
9	0.3157	0.2588	0.4489	0.4157	0.0969
10	0.1709	0.796*	0.1361	0.0036	-0.0347
11	0.6539*	0.4149	0.059	-0.0514	0.103
12	0.0295	0.7849*	0.1558	0.2384	-0.0164
13	0.7151*	-0.0007	0.0919	0.0676	0.1908
14	0.5917*	0.0198	0.376	-0.0339	0.2638
15	0.3314	0.2288	0.595*	0.0992	-0.0175
16	0.5017	-0.0228	0.5528*	0.1345	-0.015
17	0.2222	0.3278	0.1476	0.0873	0.4951*
18	0.161	0.3659	0.5691*	0.1191	0.0886
19	0.0246	0.1373	0.4126	0.5372*	-0.1939
20	0.0563	0.2272	0.4115	0.3589	-0.3929
21	0.1352	0.2175	0.1193	-0.0067	0.5938*
22	-0.0215	0.4097	0.4777	0.1474	0.2346
23	0.5176	0.4329	0.153	0.0776	0.2547
24	0.146	0.7695*	0.0239	0.1776	0.2324
25	0.3732	0.354	0.3319	0.2583	0.1765
26	0.2076	0.2715	0.6434*	0.2	0.1742
27	0.477	0.2617	0.0932	0.6005*	0.0792
28	0.0777	0.3251	0.7191*	0.2613	0.0698
29	0.3916	0.1434	-0.0372	0.5006*	0.0139
30	0.3595	0.2897	0.4341	0.2912	-0.2969
31	0.5993*	0.2366	0.2277	0.0791	-0.1447
32	0.5551*	-0.0384	-0.0424	0.1199	0.0159
33	0.325	0.6399*	0.1384	0.0559	0.0663
34	0.273	0.5618*	0.3966	0.1498	0.0961
35	-0.1726	0.7525*	0.178	0.2796	-0.1224
36	0.7152*	0.1176	0.3736	-0.0876	0.0447
37	0.557*	0.086	0.0242	0.3005	0.2267
38	0.4914	0.5853	0.2414	-0.0554	-0.2162
39	0.3037	0.6641*	0.0123	0.2119	0.0431

40	0.4702	0.4249	0.2089	0.2169	-0.1955
41	-0.0628	0.7213*	0.2869	0.0216	0.1801
42	-0.0756	0.021	0.2343	0.6862*	0.135
43	0.6006*	-0.06	0.2401	0.1005	-0.1289
44	0.3108	0.3697	0.5164*	0.0471	-0.1702
45	0.0762	0.0241	0.7251*	0.2043	0.3377
46	0.8101*	0.0141	0.1037	-0.0185	0.3112
47	0.7263*	0.0711	0.2421	-0.0973	-0.1736
48	0.4968*	0.1117	0.2372	0.1118	0.1462
49	0.0371	0.443	0.1986	0.5927*	-0.1525
50	0.4187	0.0555	0.6288*	0.0952	0.3247
51	-0.1022	0.5733*	0.2216	0.1209	0.2868
52	0.014	0.2835	0.5244*	0.2075	-0.3232
53	0.1903	-0.0519	0.2809	0.4423	0.6198*
54	0.456	0.1577	0.5837*	0.0927	0.1041
55	-0.0778	0.6706*	0.1624	-0.1581	0.0017
56	0.0235	0.6318*	0.4099	0.2023	0.3027
<i>Eigenvalue:</i>	8.64	8.33	7.43	4.52	2.90
<i>% explained variance:</i>	15.43	14.88	13.28	8.06	5.18
<i>Cumulative % explained variance</i>	15.43	30.31	43.59	51.65	56.83

S6c: Ammunition study: factor array

Comparison of factor arrays in the Ammunition study. The scores for each statement represent a weighted average derived from the contributing sorts for each factor.

Item Number	Statement	Factor	
		1	2
1	Stakeholder opinions from all sides of the lead poisoning debate should be included in any decision-making process.	2	3
2	Lead shot is better than steel at killing and not wounding an animal.	0	5
3	Supermarkets should clearly state that their wild game meat products might contain lead.	2	0
4	Lead ammunition harms the image of shooting.	1	-3
5	Steel shot is more likely to ricochet from hard surfaces than lead.	2	4
6	The phasing out of lead shot will lead to the demise of shooting.	-5	1
7	The financial impacts of any further restrictions on lead could be very damaging to shooting related interests.	-3	0
8	Lead ammunition is not a major source of lead poisoning in wild birds.	-3	1
9	There is no evidence that lead poisoning causes bird populations to decline.	-3	1
10	Current game meat handling techniques are enough to address any risks to humans from lead shot.	-1	2
11	Shooters' pastimes and activities are being eroded.	-4	2
12	If shooters saw birds dying from lead poisoning they would think twice about using lead ammunition.	4	0
13	The scientific evidence of the impacts of lead on waterbirds is robust.	1	-2
14	The shooting community probably does more for wildlife and habitats than any other group in the UK.	0	5
15	A large number of wildfowl die from lead poisoning each year.	0	-3
16	The risks to wild birds from lead ammunition have been exaggerated.	-3	3
17	Lead is a toxic substance.	5	3
18	Those with political power to influence the issue are biased in favour of keeping lead shot.	-1	-4
19	Lead poisoning is a major welfare problem for wild birds.	0	-4
20	Shooters and non-shooters have the same aim of having sustainable numbers of birds in the British countryside.	3	4
21	Steel shot damages shotgun barrels.	-1	1
22	There needs to be greater awareness within the shooting community about the harm lead poisoning does.	4	0
23	To be taken seriously, information about lead poisoning needs to come from within the shooting community.	1	1
24	There should be better enforcement of current regulations restricting the use of lead shot.	1	-2
25	Opposition to lead ammunition is driven more by a dislike of shooting than any evidence of harm.	-2	4

26	If use of non-toxic ammunition makes people more aware of good range judgement then they will shoot better.	-1	-3
27	Steel and lead shot are comparably priced.	-1	-2
28	More research should be done on the performance of non-toxic ammunition.	0	3
29	Eating game killed by lead ammunition has adverse effects on human health.	-2	-5
30	The most effective solution to reduce the risks of lead would be to replace lead shot with non-toxic alternatives.	2	-1
31	There are no safe levels of lead exposure.	1	-2
32	More guidance on different ammunition types, and techniques for their use, would reduce concerns about non-toxic shot.	2	0
33	Those selling game meat for human consumption are not very aware of possible lead contamination in their meat.	-1	-4
34	There is clearly a need for solutions to reduce the risks of lead poisoning.	3	0
35	The risks to human health from lead ammunition have been exaggerated.	-2	3
36	There should be better observance of current regulations restricting the use of lead shot.	4	-2
37	Current restrictions on using lead shot in England and Wales are not sufficient to address lead poisoning in waterbirds.	1	0
38	If you have to shoot at shorter ranges it's not as sporting or fun.	-4	-1
39	Shooting at closer range with non-toxic shot damages the meat.	-2	-1
40	Using plastic wads with non-toxic shot can cause problems with livestock.	0	2
41	Non-toxic shot is widely available.	3	2
42	The shooting community and cartridge manufacturers need to work together and come up with a viable alternative to lead shot.	0	4
43	Ballistically, alternatives to lead shot that are fit for purpose already exist.	3	-1
44	Current human health advice is enough to reduce the risks of lead shot to humans.	-1	2
45	Sooner or later, lead shot will be banned.	0	-2
46	Using non-toxic shot would have a negative financial impact on me.	-2	1
47	Non-toxic shot is ineffective against clay targets.	-5	-3
48	Regulations are essential to reducing lead poisoning in waterbirds.	3	-3
49	Lead poisoning in birds is not a big enough problem to justify current regulations.	-4	1
50	Accumulated spent lead shot in intensively shot locations should be removed from the soil to reduce environmental contamination.	-2	-4
51	Shooting organisations are afraid they will look weak if they support a ban on lead shot.	1	-1
52	I am happy to use non-lead ammunition.	4	-1
53	A wider range of non-toxic cartridges would become available if there was a ban on lead.	2	-1
54	Some 'non-toxic' alternatives to lead have greater toxicity than lead.	-3	0

55	Robust scientific evidence should determine how we use lead shot.	5	2
56	If we stopped using lead shot we'd have more birds to shoot.	-4	-5

S6d: Cat management study: factor array

Table S6d: Comparison of factor arrays in the Cat management study. The scores for each statement represent a weighted average derived from the contributing sorts for each factor. Here, the factors are presented in decreasing order of % explained variance.

	statement	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
1	I am concerned that being kept inside doesn't give cats the stimulation they need	-3	5	2	2	0
2	I've never seriously thought about whether cats affect wildlife populations	0	0	-2	-5	6
3	If my cat was killed when roaming, I would feel guilty that I hadn't prevented it	5	0	0	1	2
4	Cats that are brought up indoors are used to it	4	-2	0	0	2
5	Cats hunting doesn't bother me	-1	2	-3	-5	1
6	I worry about the effect of cats hunting on garden bird populations	-2	-2	0	6	-5
7	Cats help to keep rodent populations down	-1	4	0	2	3
8	Choosing to keep cats indoors is fine as long as the owner provides a lot of stimulation	5	-4	1	-2	0
9	When I got a cat, I didn't really think about whether it would hunt	1	-1	1	-4	4
10	I can understand some people being anti-cat because of their hunting behaviour	0	1	0	3	3
11	Keeping cats indoors keeps them safe	6	-1	-1	-3	-1
12	One cat can't do much harm to wildlife by itself	-1	0	1	-4	-2
13	Cats that bring in prey do so as a present for their owners	3	2	-1	0	5
14	Where there is vulnerable wildlife, people should not be allowed to have cats	-3	-5	-3	-1	-1
15	It is natural for cats to want to go out into the world; if they happen to fall foul of it, that's also natural	0	3	3	4	4
16	Any declines in wildlife cannot be blamed primarily on cats	2	2	2	1	1
17	Cats should be kept inside to stop them hunting	-4	-6	-5	-6	-5

18	There are too many cats in this country	-3	-3	-2	-1	-6
19	If you spend enough time with your cat, it can make a difference to the amount it hunts	0	-3	-1	0	-1
20	If you keep cats in at night they won't catch as much	1	-1	0	-1	2
21	I would only really be concerned about cats hunting if they were catching birds	-1	-3	-3	5	-1
22	When there are baby birds around, cats should be kept indoors or in restricted areas of gardens	0	-5	-3	-2	-2
23	I don't want to have to spend time playing with the cat	-5	-5	-5	-6	-3
24	Cats should be able to have the sun shining on their faces, to explore grass, to hunt insects and mice	1	6	4	4	2
25	If there was scientific evidence saying 'this species is endangered because of cats', then I would take managing my cat's hunting behaviour much more seriously	0	0	1	4	5
26	Wildlife has more of a right to life than a cat has the right to be outdoors	-5	-6	-4	-2	-4
27	Cats should be allowed out but its OK to keep them in at night	5	-2	3	0	2
28	I would be proud of my cat for hunting	-3	2	-6	-3	-3
29	Cats that go outside will hunt wild animals if they get the chance	2	3	-1	3	0
30	Collars can be dangerous for cats	1	1	2	0	-6
31	I want cats to be hunting and keeping the vermin down	-1	2	-4	0	0
32	I worry that roaming cats are at risk of being deliberately hurt by people	4	1	2	0	-3
33	I worry about roaming cats being lost, stolen or killed by traffic	6	1	3	3	5
34	I love wildlife, but hunting is just what cats do	3	4	5	1	3
35	Having to deal with prey that cats bring home is disgusting	-2	-2	1	-1	1
36	I worry about diseases that roaming cats could pick up	3	0	0	-3	-4
37	I worry that foxes will attack cats that are out at night	3	0	-2	-3	-2
38	I want a cat that comes inside, so I wouldn't want an outdoor-only cat	3	1	6	-2	3
39	I would be unhappy if my cat caused any animal to suffer	2	0	4	3	3

40	I would be more inclined to try and manage my cat's hunting if it was killing stuff all the time	-2	-1	3	5	6
41	Hunting by cats annoys me because I know they're not hungry	-2	-3	-1	-2	-4
42	If my cat brought prey home and I could rescue it, I would	4	3	6	6	2
43	Their hunting is the least attractive aspect of cat ownership	-3	-1	3	1	1
44	Some cats would prefer to be indoors	2	-1	1	-2	-1
45	Quick-release collars are no use because cats regularly lose them	-4	0	-1	-1	-2
46	Cats do not belong in the house	-6	-4	-6	-4	-5
47	The benefits to cats of going outside outweigh the risks of them getting injured or lost	-1	4	5	2	4
48	Collars with bells are bad for a cat's mental wellbeing	-4	-1	-2	-1	-4
49	Hunting is a good sign because it shows that cats are comfortable and behaving normally	2	5	-3	2	0
50	Cats should have the right to roam where they please, like a wild animal	0	6	2	2	1
51	Letting cats roam free causes havoc for our threatened wildlife	-5	-2	-4	-1	-3
52	It's straightforward to make a garden secure and cat proof	-2	-4	-5	-5	-2
53	If you choose to have a cat, and it hunts, you have to put up with it	2	4	4	0	0
54	Cats hunting is just a nuisance	-4	-3	-2	-3	0
55	Owners can't stop their cats hunting	1	3	2	-4	-2
56	Belled collars can effectively reduce the amount of animals cats catch	1	1	1	3	4
57	Keeping cats indoors is cruel	-6	2	0	1	-3
58	Cats should have free access to both the house and the outdoors	1	5	5	4	-1
59	Breeding of cats should be regulated	4	3	4	5	0
60	It is my responsibility, as an owner, to manage my cat's hunting behaviour	0	-4	-2	2	1
61	I know what owners can do to effectively control their cat's hunting	-2	-2	-4	1	-1
62	Cats are cruel to their prey	-1	1	-1	1	1